

ANALYSIS OF HYPERTENSIVE PEOPLE UNDER 60 YEARS OF AGE IN THE MUNICIPALITY OF PASSO DE CAMARAGIBE – AL/ BRAZIL, IN THE PERIOD FROM 2015 TO 2017

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Abstract:

Systemic arterial hypertension is a public health problem in Brazil and the world. The interest in researching the epidemiological profile of hypertensives attended at the health units enrolled in the Family Health Program, in the city of Passo de Camaragibe, Alagoas / Brazil, came up due to the increasing number of this pathology in the population, especially among young adults. The research aims to analyze the profile of hypertensive patients, with emphasis on the population under 60 years old, in the period from 2015 to 2017, determining the aggravations that most affect this group. The study is bibliographic, documentary, and descriptive, observational, with a quantitative approach. The data were collected in the medical records and registration forms of the six health units of the county. The results showed a relatively high number of young adults with HAS (Systemic Arterial Hypertension), with a higher percentage in the female group, besides a considerable number of hypertensive patients who also present Diabetes, obesity, and cardiovascular diseases associated with HAS. It was observed that the existing public policies in the county are still insufficient, especially when it comes to prevention. In front of this situation, it is suggested to apply some actions to prevent HAS in the young population, as the implementation of a schedule with defined service, educational activities at alternative times, and local activities groups, with the support of the community health agent. Given the profile of this population found in this study, it is necessary to implement these suggested actions to involve more effective assistance to a portion of the economically active and expressive population.

Keywords: Central Nervous System. Lymphoma. Metastasis

INTRODUCTION

Systemic Arterial Hypertension (HAS) can be considered a relevant public health problem in Brazil and worldwide. Estimates indicate that its prevalence is on the rise and its impact on populations will be even more damaging in the coming years. The constant analysis and collection of information about this health problem are of fundamental importance for health planners and managers (BOING; BOING, 2007).

HAS is responsible for the origin of many non-communicable chronic diseases, in addition to being a direct cause of hypertensive heart disease, it is a risk factor for diseases resulting from arteriosclerosis and thrombosis, which are predominantly manifested by ischemic heart, cerebrovascular, peripheral vascular, and renal. Due to hypertensive and ischemic heart disease, it is also an etiologic factor of heart failure. Therefore, it characterizes it as one of the causes of greater reduction in the life expectancy of individuals (DUNCAN; SCHIMIDT; GIUGLIANE, 2006).

The number of chronic noncommunicable diseases (NCDs) is growing all over the world and, consequently, the health of populations suffers from this impact. Approximately 35 million people died in 2005 from this cause, with 80% of these deaths in low- and middle-income countries. Systemic arterial hypertension (HAS) is one of the most common chronic diseases and with the most serious clinical repercussions. It is estimated that, worldwide, 7.1 million people die annually from high blood pressure, and that 4.5% of the disease burden in the world is caused by HAS. Among the main complications of HAS are acute myocardial infarction (AMI), stroke (CVA), and chronic renal failure (CRF) (BOING; BOING, 2007).

HAS has contributing factors for its appearance in different aspects, such as increased weight gain, lack of physical activity, Diabetes mellitus, as well as being a risk factor for the onset of chronic diseases, especially cardiovascular ones. It reaches people from all economic classes and is reaching an increasingly younger public.

Given these facts, it is important to go deeper into the characteristics of patients with chronic noncommunicable diseases, as a means of finding out about the causes, consequences, treatments, and preventive methods of these diseases. Thus, this work will aim to analyze the profile of

hypertensive patients, with emphasis on the population under 60 years of age, assisted by the ESF (Family Health Strategy), in the municipality of Passo de Camaragibe, determining the health problems in which these hypertensive patients have already been affected. as a result of the underlying pathology.

METHODS

This study is a bibliographic and documental review, where data were collected through a search in the main health databases, including websites of official bodies. From the survey of information, a descriptive analysis of the indicators of hypertensive patients in the municipality of Passo de Camaragibe, Brazil, can be carried out.

To carry out the analysis, it was verified, through a case history, the number of male and female patients, under the age of 60 years, who were diagnosed with hypertension, between the years of 2015 and 2017, allowing a statistical analysis.

As all hypertensive patients included in the research are monitored by the health units and met the inclusion criteria, who lived in the city, had a diagnosis of hypertension and be monitored by the ESF, and there was no one excluded, as the exclusion criteria were based on users who were still in the investigative process, without a confirmed diagnosis and/or incomplete records, the sample was considered as the total number of hypertensive patients, equal to the population. After applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, we reached a total sample of 1448 hypertensive individuals. (n=1448).

After authorization from the Municipal Health Department to carry out the research, data collection took place through the analysis of medical records and files of community health agents, which correspond to the register of families enrolled in their micro-area, where community agents have control over the hypertensive patients assisted by the health unit. The units have control of their hypertensive patients through registration forms, which contain data such as patient identification and prescribed treatment. Each micro-area is responsible for a community health agent, with a total of 39 agents. The researcher had access to these records at the health units, as each unit has its file.

The municipality has 6 health units, with a

total of 39 community health agents, with the following distribution:

- **PSF 1 – Health Unit Ciridião Durval**
Located in the Centro district, comprising seven micro areas, responsible for the assistance of 1149 families. Each micro-area has a health agent in charge.

- **PSF 2 – Health Unit Maria Luiza Durval**
Localizada no Distrito Barra de Camaragibe, zona rural e litorânea de Passo de Camaragibe, composta por sete microáreas, responsável pelo atendimento de 811 famílias.

- **PSF 3 – Health Unit Severino Manuel**
Located in Povoado Jundiá, a rural area of Passo de Camaragibe, composed of five macro-areas, responsible for serving 239 families. Each micro-area has a health agent in charge.

- **PSF 4 – Health Unit Carlos Souza Silver**
Located in the Centro district, comprising eight micro areas, responsible for the assistance to 1197 families. Each micro-area has a health agent in charge.

- **PSF 5 – Health Unit Paulo Sebastião dos Santos**
Located in Povoado Bom Despacho, a rural area of Passo de Camaragibe, comprising six microareas, responsible for serving 420 families. Each microarea has a health agent in charge.

- **PSF 6 – Unidade de Saúde Maria Elisa da Silva**
Located in Povoado Unussu, a rural area of Passo de Camaragibe, comprising six micro-areas, responsible for serving 327 families. Each micro-area has a health agent in charge.

The research was based on the consolidation of existing records in each health unit. The researcher sought the records referring to hypertensive patients in each unit, which serve as a control both for health agents, who monitor these users Every month, and for health professionals, who attend to them directly at the unit.

The study was submitted for evaluation on the Plataforma Brasil website, approved under opinion number: 2,301,430.

RESULTS

HAS has contributing factors for its

appearance in different aspects, such as increased weight gain, lack of physical activity, Diabetes mellitus, as well as being a risk factor for the onset of chronic diseases, especially cardiovascular ones. It reaches people from all economic classes and is reaching an increasingly younger public.

The city, even with a profile of a small and rural city, had a considerable number of hypertensive patients, with emphasis on the number of hypertensive patients under 60 years of age, confirming that chronic diseases no longer affect only the elderly, but come reaching many young adults.

Table 1 - Consolidated of all health units. Data was collected between October and November 2017, through the files of the health units themselves.

	PSF*1	PSF*2	PSF*3	PSF*4	PSF*5	PSF*6	TOTAL
N total de hypertensive	360	261	114	445	179	89	1449
Masculine	140	89	40	173	67	32	541
Female	220	172	74	272	112	57	907
hypertensive under 60 years old	160	130	76	177	66	45	1449
hypertensive under 60 years old who have already suffered a stroke**	08	00	01	02	05	02	18
hypertensive individual under 60 years of age who have associated DIA***	39	25	09	51	13	04	141
hypertensive individual under 60 years of age who have associated cardiovascular problems	03	04	03	03	00	01	14
hypertensive individual under 60 years of age who are obese	04	09	05	07	11	01	37

*PSF: Family Health Program, referring to each health unit.
**AVE: Brain stroke.
***DIA: Diabetes mellitus.

The survey managed to reveal that females have a higher number of hypertension compared to men. Among the various factors, the diagnosis in women ends up being faster, because it is a group that attends health units more often.

In a survey in the Rio Grande do Sul - Brazil, it was found that more than 50% of the women surveyed, regarding hypertension,

were aged between 20 and 39 years, and that more than half of these women (51%) had at least one of the hypertensive parents (HARTMANN et al., 2007).

In the research carried out by Boing and Boing (2007), it was possible to verify the predominance of women registered in the Hiperdia program, in all age groups, with the greatest difference in age between 40 and 49 years. In the year investigated, 387,754 patients were registered in the System, with 66% (255,830) women and 34% (131,924) men (BOING; BOING, 2007).

In the study by Gomes and Silva (2010), it was proved that a greater number of female patients with arterial hypertension can maintain control of the disease. (GOMES; ROCHA E SILVA; SANTOS, 2010).

Another criterion researched was the association of diseases that are usually associated with patients with Systemic Arterial Hypertension (HAS), such as Diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular problems, and obesity. Of the 654 hypertensive individuals under 60 years of age, 141 have associated diabetes mellitus, with diagnostic confirmation and taking medication; 18 have already suffered a stroke, characterizing the lack of control over this hypertension; 14 use medication for cardiovascular diseases, and 37 have some degree of obesity.

The research also showed that the numbers are similar in all units, being proportional to the population quantity, with no differentiation between rural and urban areas. Both presented considerably high numbers regarding the studied diseases.

Many hypertensive patients in Brazil are still not adequately controlling the disease. It is estimated that 18 million individuals have systemic arterial hypertension, but only 30% are under control, thereby increasing the risk of stroke, Kidney, and cardiovascular diseases (MIRANZI et al., 2008).

Hypertension and Diabetes mellitus are the most common chronic diseases, whose treatment and control require behavioral changes concerning diet, medication intake, and lifestyle (MIRANZI et al., 2008).

According to the SUS (Unified Health System), Diabetes mellitus appears as the sixth primary cause of hospital admissions

and contributes significantly (30%-50%) to other causal factors of admission, such as ischemic heart disease, failure heart disease, cholecystography, stroke, and arterial hypertension (LYRA et al., 2010).

CVA is the main cause of hospitalizations, mortality, and dysfunctionality, surpassing other heart diseases and cancer. Remembering that HAS contributes as the main risk factor for the development of stroke. (MENDONÇA; LIMA; OLIVEIRA, 2012).

Marte and Santos (2007), in their research, cites the study by Framingham, who reports that, among individuals with arterial hypertension, cardiovascular events occurred more frequently in the presence of at least two risk factors, proving that the risk of events is proportional to the aggregation of risk factors. Correlation between lipid profile and systemic blood pressure is also reported, as noted in metabolic syndrome; as this syndrome always associates HAS with abdominal adiposity, hypertriglyceridemia, low HDL-C, and altered fasting glucose, it justifies the higher risk of progression to Diabetes mellitus and cardiovascular disease (MARTE; SANTOS, 2007).

Other factors not detailed in the results, but which should be highlighted, are education and socioeconomic status.

Citing the research by Gomes and Santos (2010), an interesting fact, analyzed by them in their study, was how the level of education influences the control of hypertension. Reaching surprising numbers, fifty percent of uncontrolled patients are illiterate, whereas, among controlled hypertensive patients, the illiteracy rate drops to 19%. Blood pressure control increased in proportion to the level of education, reaching 100% among those with complete secondary education (GOMES; ROCHA E SILVA; SANTOS, 2010).

The growing increase in CNCDs especially affects people with lower income and education, as they are the most exposed to risk factors and with less access to information and health services, further accentuating social inequalities (MALTA; SILVA JR, 2013).

Education is a major factor in the treatment of chronic diseases. According to the 2001 Primary Care Report, treatment adherence tends to be lower in individuals with low

education levels, which increases the responsibility of primary care professionals to develop educational activities, with an emphasis on disease control and promotion of health. Since the lower the level of education, the greater the difficulty in understanding the pathology (MIRANZI et al., 2008).

Another factor that must be taken into account is the socioeconomic status of these individuals, as their lifestyle has a great influence on the effectiveness of the treatment. Socioeconomic status is decisive for non-adherence to treatment, and a low socioeconomic level is related to a higher prevalence of HAS (MIRANZI et al., 2008).

Although the ESF (Family Health Strategy) presents public policies aimed at hypertensive patients, being considered by the health units a priority care group, the numbers of primary or secondary hypertensive patients continue to grow, with a consequent increase in the lack of quality of social life and professional, especially when affected in the economically active phase, yet another reason to invest in research aimed at this group. Notably, chronic diseases are at a level of comfort, even for health professionals, and this research serves to boost enthusiasm in caring for people with chronic diseases.

Even though the SUS (Unified Health System) is a free and universal system in Brazil, the individual cost of chronic disease is still considerably high, due to the aggregate costs, which contributes to the impoverishment of families. For the health system, the direct costs of CNCs (Chronic NonCommunicable Diseases) represent a growing impact. In Brazil, CNCs are among the main causes of hospital admissions (MALTA; MORAIS NETO; SILVA JUNIOR, 2011)

Despite the rapid growth of CNCs, through comprehensive and cost-effective health promotion interventions, their impact can be reversed, providing reduction of risk factors, improved health care, early detection, and timely treatment (MALTA; MORAIS NETO; SILVA JUNIOR, 2011).

CONCLUSION

About hypertensive individuals under 60 years of age, an increase was observed, with a total number of 654 confirmed cases, which is equivalent to 45.17% of the total

number of hypertensive individuals in the city. The study also allowed the identification of hypertensive individuals under 60 years of age and with associated diseases such as Diabetes mellitus (mean 10%), obesity (2.55%), cardiovascular problems (0.96%), and 18 cases of Stroke, which is considered high for a population under 60 years of age, and a short study period, 2 years.

With the collected data, it was possible to determine the diseases whose hypertensive individuals under 60 years of age have already been affected as a result of the underlying disease, extremely relevant information, due to the impact generated on public health programs.

The survey revealed that there is a significant rate of hypertensive individuals under 60 years of age. The number shown symbolizes an alert to the need for closer monitoring of these patients and the development of an action plan that enables a reduction in the picture presented, to imply more effective care for a portion of the economically active and expressive population.

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